

MORPHO-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESISTANCE BACTERIA TO VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF Cr CATIONS

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Abstract. This study examines the sensitivity and viability of various microbial strains – *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94, and *Pseudomonas putida* 133 – to different concentrations of chromium ions. The results indicate that these local bacterial strains demonstrate potential effect in the bioremediation of soils contaminated with chromium ions.

Keywords: chromium, bacteria, toxicity, *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94, *Pseudomonas putida* 133.

Heavy metals and their compounds are significant environmental pollutants with various negative impacts on human health. Due to their high toxicity and capacity to accumulate in soil, plants, animals, and humans, heavy metals are classified among the most hazardous chemical contaminants [1]. Notable examples include fluorine, vanadium, chromium, manganese, cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, arsenic, molybdenum, cadmium, mercury, lead, tungsten, and iron. The primary sources of soil contamination with heavy metals include industrial waste, combustion products, vehicle emissions, and agricultural chemicals [2].

Chromium (Cr) exists in various valence states in the environment, with the most stable forms being Cr (VI) and Cr (III). Hexavalent chromium (Cr (VI)) is particularly toxic and is the main contributor to chromium-related pollution [3]. Common soil compounds, such as HCrO_4^- and CrO_4^{2-} , are easily absorbed by plants and significantly contribute to soil contamination [4]. Chromium is classified as a class A carcinogen due to its toxicity. While trivalent chromium (Cr (III)) can enhance insulin activity and reduce diabetes risk, excessive levels can lead to long-term toxicity and carcinogenicity [5]. Cr (VI) can enter the human body through inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact, accumulating in various organs and systems and leading to pathological conditions and increased cancer risk [6].

Absorption of Cr by plants negatively affects their growth and development, causing wilting of stem cells [7].

This study investigates the resistance of microbial strains – *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94, and *Pseudomonas putida* 133 – to different concentrations of chromium ions.

Object of the Study: The study focused on the strains *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94, and *Pseudomonas putida* 133, which are part of the microbial collection at the Institute of Microbiology. These strains were isolated from soil samples collected near chemical enterprises in Samarkand and Kashkadarya regions.

Cultivation of Microorganisms:

The nutrient medium composition (g/l) was as follows: L-glucose – 10; K₂HPO₄ – 0.5; MgSO₄·7H₂O – 0.5; NaCl – 0.5; peptone – 5; agar-agar – 20. The nutrient medium was sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C (0.5 ATM) for 15-20 minutes. Potassium chromate (K₂CrO₄) was used as the source of heavy metal salts. The different concentrations of heavy metal salts were dissolved in distilled water, sterilized in boiling water vapor for 10 minutes, and added to the nutrient medium. The medium was thoroughly mixed, cooled to a temperature comfortable to the touch, and poured into sterile Petri dishes (20 ml per dish) under sterile conditions.

In this experiment, the selected bacterial cultures were first grown in liquid peptone broth (PB) for 24 hours at 28-30°C. After incubation, 1 ml of the culture suspensions was diluted in 9 ml of sterile distilled water. Dilutions were prepared until 10⁵-10⁸ CFU/ml depending on the growth rate of the culture. A drop of the diluted culture suspensions was then added to the nutrient agar plates, and the bacteria were spread using the lawn method with a sterile spatula.

Furthermore, the experiments were conducted in triplicate under both control and heavy metal conditions. The strains were inoculated under conditions where the chromium concentration was 3 times higher (67.224 mg/l), 5 times higher (112.04 mg/l), and 10 times higher (224.08 mg/l) than the permissible quantity (PQ). Noticeable that PQ of this metal is 22.408 mg/l. After inoculation, the Petri dishes were incubated at 27-30°C. Visible colonies began to appear after 24 hours, but under heavy metal conditions, colony growth was delayed and observed only after 48 hours.

This experiment relied on visual inspection to assess significant differences and changes in colony morphology under varying levels of chromium exposure. Moreover, the experiment relied on visual inspection, which revealed significant differences and noticeable changes in the appearance of the colonies.

Results: Visual observations of the growth of *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10 strain revealed that, under control conditions, the colonies were cream-colored, round, flower-shaped, and ranged in diameter from 1.3 mm to 8 mm. At chromium concentrations 3 PQ (67.224 mg/l), 5 PQ (112.04 mg/l), and 10 PQ (224.08 mg/l) times higher than the PQ, the number of colonies decreased, and their shape became irregular and cloudy, with sizes ranging from 3-5 mm up to 3 cm. Additionally, a void was observed in the center of the colonies.

Microscopic analysis confirmed that *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10 is a gram-positive bacterium. Under heavy metal stress, compared to the control, the cell shape changed, with the rod-shaped cells becoming elongated and bent (Table 1).

Table 1. Morpho-cultural characteristics of Bacteria

Name of microorganisms	Control	Cr (PQ ≥3)	Cr (PQ ≥5)	Cr (PQ ≥10)
<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i> 10				

Picture 1. You should give name of this picture and describe details. Please number each one

Bacillus cereus 17: Under control conditions, *Bacillus cereus* 17 colonies appeared creamy, shiny, and round, with diameters ranging from 2 mm to 8 mm. However, at chromium concentrations 3 (67.224 mg/l), 5 (112.04 mg/l), and 10 (224.08 mg/l) times higher than the PQ, the number of colonies decreased while their size increased, with diameters ranging from 6 mm to 10 mm. The edges of the colonies became uneven, and the center turned white and transparent. Moreover, *Bacillus cereus* 17 is a gram-positive bacterium that also exhibited changes in cell shape under heavy metal stress compared to the control. In the control conditions, the cells were short rod-like structures measuring 2-5 μm in length. Under high concentrations of chromium, a significant difference was observed, with cells elongating to 2-8 μm and adopting a more extended rod-like appearance.

Bacillus thuringiensis 94: The colonies of *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94 strain were cream-colored, round, and cloudy in appearance, with relatively uniform diameters under control conditions. Under conditions with chromium concentrations 3 (67.224 mg/l), 5 (112.04 mg/l), and 10 (224.08 mg/l) times higher than PQ, the colonies became irregular, cloudy, and displayed

hyphae-like growth patterns extending from the center to the periphery. *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94 is a gram-positive bacterium, and significant differences were noted in the cell morphology. In the control, the cells were short, rod-shaped, and exhibited a mucous, viscous texture. Under heavy metal conditions, individual elongated cells measuring 2-5 μm were observed.

Pseudomonas putida 133: The colonies of *Pseudomonas putida* 133 were spherical and displayed a slower growth rate compared to *Bacillus species*, with visible growth after 48 hours at chromium concentrations 3 times higher than PQ (67.224 mg/l). At higher concentrations (PLM \geq 5 and PLM \geq 10), growth was observed only after 72 hours. *Pseudomonas putida* 133 typically produces a yellow-green pigment during growth; however, under chromium stress at 3 (67.224 mg/l), 5 (112.04 mg/l), and 10 (224.08 mg/l) times higher than PQ, pigment production ceased, and the colonies became smaller and diffusely spread. *Pseudomonas putida* 133 is a gram-negative bacterium, and microscopic examination revealed that, in control conditions, the cells were rod-shaped and measured 2-4 μm in length. Under heavy metal stress, the cells became smaller and more densely packed at concentrations 5 (112.04 mg/l) and 10 (224.08 mg/l) times higher than PLM.

The reduction of Cr (VI) is known to be a primary detoxification mechanism, achieved through direct reduction by electron-donating groups and indirect reduction involving the binding of anionic Cr (VI) species to positively charged functional groups on the biomass surface, followed by reduction to Cr (III). Heavy metal toxicity is generally associated with intracellular metal concentrations, and tolerance is influenced by either attenuation or enhancement of metal bioaccumulation [8]. Additionally, under heavy metal stress, changes in cellular activity can lead to morphological anomalies in microorganisms, often manifested as alterations in shape and size. For instance, *Escherichia coli* grown in environments with high heavy metal concentrations can develop unusual filamentous forms, typically resulting from disruptions in cell growth and division processes in the presence of heavy metals.

In conclusion, the strains studied – *Bacillus paralicheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94, and *Pseudomonas putida* 133 – demonstrated the ability to grow and develop at high chromium concentrations (67.224 mg/l; 112.04 mg/l; 224.08 mg/l). Given their competitive growth and biosorption capacities, (I think you should reverse this words because you did not determine and enter biosorption datas of these microorganisms) these local strains hold potential for future in bioremediation processes for soils contaminated with chromium ions.

REFERENCES

1. Khalikulov, Sh.T., & Nematov, Kh.M. (2022). Soil contamination with heavy metals. Proceedings of the Republican Scientific and Practical Conference on Theoretical and Practical Principles of Innovative Development of the Agricultural Sector in Uzbekistan. Samarkand Branch of Tashkent State Agrarian University, October 5-6, 2022, 774-777. (In Uzbek).
2. Bakhranov G.M. Soil contamination with heavy metals and its impact on the environment // Academic Research in Educational Sciences VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 10 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1385 Scientific Journal Impact Factor (SJIF) 2021: 5.723 Directory Indexing of International Research Journals-CiteFactor 2020-21: 0.89 DOI: 10.24412/2181-1385-2021-10-193-196., 193-196 (In Uzbek).

3. Chen, F.; Ma, J.; Akhtar, S.; Khan, Z.I.; Ahmad, K.; Ashfaq, A.; Nawaz, H.; Nadeem, M. Assessment of chromium toxicity and potential health implications of agriculturally diversely irrigated food crops in the semi-arid regions of South Asia. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2022, 272, 107833.
4. Sharma, P.; Singh, S.P.; Parakh, S.K.; Tong, Y.W. Health hazards of hexavalent chromium (Cr (VI)) and its microbial reduction. *Bioengineered* 2022, 13, 4923-4938.
5. Deng, Y.; Wang, M.; Tian, T.; Lin, S.; Xu, P.; Zhou, L.; Dai, C.; Hao, Q.; Wu, Y.; Zhai, Z.; et al. The Effect of Hexavalent Chromium on the Incidence and Mortality of Human Cancers: A Meta-Analysis Based on Published Epidemiological Cohort Studies. *Front. Oncol.* 2019, 9, 24.
6. Kapoor RT, Bani Mfarrej MF, Alam P, Rinklebe J, Ahmad P. Accumulation of chromium in plants and its repercussion in animals and humans. *Environ Pollut.* 2022 May 15; 301:119044. doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119044. Epub 2022 Feb 23. PMID: 35217142.
7. Ao, M.; Chen, X.; Deng, T.; Sun, S.; Tang, Y.; Morel, J.L.; Qiu, R.; Wang, S. Chromium biogeochemical behaviour in soil-plant systems and remediation strategies: A critical review. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 2022, 424, 127233.
8. Li XZ, Plésiat P, Nikaido H. The challenge of efflux-mediated antibiotic resistance in Gram-negative bacteria. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2015 Apr; 28(2):337-418. doi: 10.1128/CMR.00117-14.